

Flood risk for urban mobility in Maputo, Mozambique: Regional-scale indexing based on earth observation and demographic data

Marianna Loli, Dr¹, Stergios Aristoteles Mitoulis, Dr
University of Surrey

George Kefalas, Dr
International Hellenic University

Elena Bouzoni
Grid Engineers

Leon Kapetas, Dr
Resilient Cities Network

Guillermo Diaz-Fanas, Fatima Arroyo Arroyo
The World Bank

ABSTRACT

In Mozambique, extreme weather events have a measurable impact on social and economic growth. Triggered by cyclones and intense rain events, floods have become more frequent in recent years and are expected to follow this trend due to climate change. Recently, major floods following the passage of cyclones Idai and Kenneth (2019) caused 603 fatalities, leaving 1641 people injured and 2.5 million people in need of humanitarian aid, of which 1.3 million were children. At the capital, Maputo, and the surrounding cities and districts (Matola, Marracuene, and Boane) that form the Greater Maputo Area (GMA) accessibility to jobs, health, and education facilities for the poorest population is one of the lowest in Africa, with one-third of public transport users reporting that flooding hinders their access to jobs during rainy days. A methodical investigation of flood risk for the existing road network in Matola and Maputo has been conducted in the framework of a major urban development project planned by the Government of Mozambique. Assessment of flood hazard has been carried out in GIS using the Flood Hazard Index framework based on geomorphological, meteorological, hydrological, and geographical criteria, as well as inventorying of historic floods. To account for climate change, baseline calculations are compared with projections up to 2040. The analysis has considered the exposure of the population in addition to the geospatial distribution of the primary and secondary road network. Socioeconomic parameters relevant to poverty and the presence of vulnerable groups have been considered for the estimation of human vulnerability. The paper presents a novel implementation of the INFORM risk indexing framework for the analysis of flood-induced transportation disruptions in a region where the humanitarian impact of such events can be disproportionate. The outcome of this study is expected to be useful for an equity-centred prioritization of climate adaptation interventions to enhance the resilience and inclusivity of urban transport systems in GMA.

Keywords: Flooding, Social vulnerability, Risk, Climate change, Socio-economic inequalities, Urban mobility

¹ email: m.loli@surrey.ac.uk

INTRODUCTION

Based on a global analysis of flood risk, Rentschler & Salhab (2020) estimate that 1.47 billion people, i.e. 19% of the world population, would experience some level of inundation that would pose a significant risk to life during a 1-in-100 year flood event. Over 1/3 of these people are also impacted by extreme poverty, living on less than \$5.50 a day (Bailey et al., 2021).

In Sub-Saharan Africa, where flooding is currently affecting an estimated 71 million people who also live in extreme poverty, climate change is a serious threat to societal wellbeing and peace. Mozambique is one of the region's hot spots and one of the most high-risk countries in the world (JRC, 2021). It is threatened by manmade as well as natural disasters — including floods, cyclones, droughts, and wildfires — while its people are highly vulnerable due to economic deprivation, food insecurity, and inequality. Furthermore, their capacity to cope with hazards is limited due to the lack of essential infrastructure which hinders mobility, communication, and access to healthcare. At the same time, the country is urbanizing at a rapid pace. As a result, its economic and social development has become highly dependent on the commercial and industrial activity that is concentrated at its capital, Maputo, and the surrounding municipalities (Matola, Marracuene, and Boane) that form the Greater Maputo Area (GMA). Yet, population growth and the associated rising demand for transport has not been backed with the needed investment to environmentally sustainable and inclusive transportation services. As a result, accessibility to jobs, health, and education facilities for the poorest population in GMA is one of the lowest in Africa, with a substantial proportion of public transport users reporting that flooding hinders their access to jobs during rainy days.

Climate adaptation and risk reduction in disaster-prone developing countries must be built on a sound understanding of the drivers of humanitarian risk so that decision-makers can work from a common understanding of priorities to exploit resources in a coordinated and effective manner. As part of a major urban mobility project, planned by the Government of Mozambique (GoM) financed by the World Bank, we carried out Flood Hazard Indexing (FHI) for the GMA. This involves the identification and mapping of flood-prone areas based on a statistical analysis of the controlling factors, namely intrinsic territorial characteristics, such as slope, elevation, river network, and land use, in addition to precipitation.

Assessment of flood hazard at the watershed level by use of fluid mechanic modelling of floodplain inundation is a challenging and resource-demanding exercise (Bates, 2022). In recent years, statistical approaches to flood susceptibility have become an increasingly popular alternative (e.g.: Arabameri et al., 2019; Dodangeh et al., 2020; Lyu et al., 2018; Mahmoud & Gan, 2018; Phongsapan et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2018) due to their limited requirement for data, in comparison to conventional rainfall–runoff modelling methods, and ability to build upon public earth observation datasets to conduct the analysis at a regional scale. In this study, FHI has been based on a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), implemented in GIS, in conjunction with the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), following Kazakis et al. (2015).

Decision-making for flood resilience and adaptation must be based on the analysis of risk, of which hazard is only one component. In addition to the exposure of humans and infrastructure, in this study we incorporate socio-economic parameters, considering human vulnerabilities and inequalities driven by income, age, and health conditions. We use climate change projections consistent with a detrimental scenario for future emissions and global socio-economic development to highlight the likely dramatic increase of the region's flood susceptibility by 2040 and the increasing urgency to adapt to climate impacts and build resilience for the communities.

STUDY AREA

The Infulene river serves as the boundary between the municipalities of Maputo and Matola. Its drainage basin, highlighted in Fig. 1(a), has an area of 302 km² and includes Maputo city, the capital, which is the country's political and industrial center. Nevertheless, mobility across the region is inadequate, sparse and of low reliability, due to its deficit road network. A significant proportion of roads in Maputo and Matola are unpaved and in poor condition. What is more, drainage infrastructure is scarce while the functionality of the very few roadside trenches is often compromised by debris blockages due to lack of maintenance. As a result, rainfall events lead to widespread flooding (examples shown in Fig. 1(b) – (e)), causing severe disruptions due to the inundation of roads, even along primary roads and central arteries (Fig. 1(b)).

Based on interviews with over 200 residents and 100 frequent travelers carried out in 2015, the Municipality of Matola mapped flood susceptible locations in the region, especially focusing on mapping problematic sections of the road network. The study indicates that during the rainy season (October – March) flood induced travel disruptions become a routine. Many users reported that, in addition to being unable to use their old cars when streets are inundated, flooding also restricts their access to public transport. Certain parts of the network (highlighted in Fig. 1(a)) remain inundated for days, leading to sustained isolation of people, who report this as a significant obstruction of access to opportunities. Furthermore, the livability and safety of nearby residential houses deteriorate tremendously, as water remains inside houses and backyards for days. Reflective of the situation is the municipality’s statement that “the rainy season causes panic to spread among a considerable part of Matola’s citizens.”

Figure 1. (a) The studied area and photos of inundated roads across Maputo [source: Quadrante, 2014] (b) central avenue; (c) residential area, (d) the National library and (e) a primary school.

ANALYSIS IN GIS

Following the methodological framework of Fig. 2, we exploit remotely sensed imagery, public datasets (climate data, topography and geology maps, and street maps), socioeconomic datasets (census, locations of critical facilities) and flood inventory maps provided by the GoM (Fig. 1(a)) to establish a database for analysis in GIS.

Figure 2. Methodology flow chart.

Flood Hazard Index (FHI)

Flood hazard assessment is one of the four components of our approach to flood risk (Fig. 2). We adopt the methodology proposed by Kazakis et al., (2015) to estimate FHI based on seven conditioning parameters, namely: i) ground elevation; (ii) ground slope; (iii) flow accumulation; (iv) land use/cover; (v) distance from the drainage network/streams; (vi) geology; and (vii) rainfall. Contoured layers of the individual thematic maps are shown in Fig. 3.

There is an inverse relationship between elevation and flood susceptibility (Li et al., 2011). The latest global Digital Elevation Model (DEM) published by Hawker et al., (2022) has a spatial resolution of 30 m and is a significant improvement to the Copernicus Digital Elevation Model thanks to the removal of “noise” caused by the presence of buildings and forests. This DEM was processed in QGIS to create the map layers of elevation (Fig. 3(a)) and ground slope (Fig. 3(b)). The latter is a physiographic characteristic that controls runoff velocity in such a way that the velocity increases with increasing the slope gradient.

The chances of flooding become higher near rivers and streams. The Channel Network algorithm available in QGIS was used to locate the network of streams in the study area through the processing of the DEM. A threshold of 1000 cells was used for the plot of Fig. 3(c). The proximity algorithm was used to calculate the distance from streams (Fig. 3(e)) assuming a lack of man-made drainage infrastructure.

Land use is a key variable controlling the amount of water runoff in comparison to precipitation. Runoff increases with the degree of environmental built-up and, hence, flooding becomes less likely in densely vegetated areas. A land use/land cover (LULC) map of the study area was created to take this parameter into account using objected-oriented image classification of high-resolution satellite images (Sentinel 2). Here, LULC has been characterized and classified into six categories, as shown in Fig.3(d). In this study, we ignored the effect of geology (soil permeability) because the region is characterized by loose structures of alluvial and coastal deposits with practically uniform permeability (JICA, 2014).

Each one of the flood conditioning parameters is classified in Table 1 (see Fig. 3) under five classes, ranging from very high to very low flood susceptibility as follows: 1 “very high flood susceptibility”, 2 “high flood susceptibility”, 3 “moderate flood susceptibility”, 4 “low flood susceptibility” and 5 “very low flood susceptibility”. The layers of Fig.3 were synthesized to produce a flood hazard map using AHP, a semi-quantitative MCDA method in which each parameter is assigned a weight factor w_i , ranging from 0 to 1. The weight of each parameter is defined after ranking and systematic pair-wise comparison of relative importance (Saaty & Vargas, 1998). The accuracy of each pairwise comparison can be assessed through the consistency index, which is a measure of departure from the consistency of pairwise judgments in the comparison matrices (Saaty, 1990). FHI is then calculated using Equation 1.

$$FHI = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i r_i \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of parameters, w_i is the weight of each parameter, and r_i is the rating of the parameter at each cell.

Table 1 lists the weights assigned to each parameter for the calculation of FHI in this study, yielding a consistency ratio $CI=0.07$ (which is lower than 0.1, as recommended by Kazakis et al., 2015). Flow accumulation and distance from streams are considered the most important parameters, in alignment with several relevant studies. Rainfall and LULC are next in the hierarchy while slope and elevation are considered the least important criteria for flooding in what is a rather flat region with an average elevation of only 20 m above the sea level. The method adopted has the advantage of being easily adjustable and tailored to the characteristics of the application. Therefore, the provided ranking and weighting parameters can be refined in future studies if additional measurements of flood inundation become available.

Current versus future climate

Figure 3(f) shows the spatial distribution of precipitation in the study area. The average wettest month precipitation from 1970 – 2000, as retrieved from WorldClim, has been taken here as the baseline scenario for rainfall intensity. It is worth noting the considerable amounts of rainfall, as monthly accumulated values reach up to 160 mm. The resulting FHI is plotted in Fig. 4(a). A reasonably good comparison is achieved between locations of predicted very high/high flood susceptibility and the historic records of past floods. It should be noted that the lack of historic flood evidence in regions where we predict high susceptibility is not a certain indicator of inaccurate prediction, due to possible under-reporting of flooding occurrences.

Figure 4(a) superimposes the primary and secondary road network (retrieved from OpenStreetMap via the OSMnx python package) to illustrate its exposure to flooding. Notably, only 30% of the over 340 km long road network crosses areas of very low to low flood susceptibility. By contrast, a very significant proportion of the network, estimated at 45% of its total length, is currently exposed to very high or high flood susceptibility.

Future climate is uncertain, yet projections show a more or less impactful intensification of storm events over time. O’Neill et al., (2016) developed the shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) framework as an update and a substantial expansion over the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). Available through Phase 6 of the World Climate Research Program Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6), the SSP framework contains multi-model climate projections based on five alternative/plausible scenarios of future emissions and land-use changes, by which society and ecosystems will evolve in the 21st century.

Figure 4(b) shows the worst-case scenario (SSP5-8.5) for precipitation in GMA up to 2040. A substantial rise, of about 20 mm on average, is projected, corresponding to significant amplification of flood hazard as illustrated in Fig. 4(b). A dramatic expansion of highly susceptible areas is predicted under this future climate scenario, while very few locations remain safe from flooding. Areas of low or medium flood hazard exposure today, appear to be shifted to higher hazard exposure in the future. As a result, GMA may see a dramatic rise in flooding in road segments that appear to be floodproof today. Calculations under SSP5-8.5 show that as much as 70% of the existing road network in GMA, i.e a threefold increase compared to current estimates, may be highly exposed to flooding in 18 years from now. This is a particularly alarming prediction calling for immediate investment to flood resilience and climate adaptation of the transport network as well as urban development in GMA.

Figure 3. Maps of parameters included in the FHI analysis: (a) elevation, (b) slope, (c) flow accumulation, (d) land use-land cover, (e) distance from streams, (f) baseline rainfall scenario, (g) 2040 rainfall projection under SSP5-8.5.

Figure 4. Flood Hazard Index (FHI) map of the Infulene catchment for the (a) baseline climate scenario and (b) for the 2021 – 2040 climate projection assuming the most pessimistic socioeconomic and climate predictions, as per the SSP5-8.5 scenario.

RISK ANALYSIS IN LIGHT OF SOCIOECONOMIC VULNERABILITIES

Natural hazards impact disproportionately the most vulnerable populations and deepen social inequalities (Cremen et al., 2022; Wing et al., 2022). In Maputo, inequalities have a long history, originating from colonial times. Social division and polarization are evident in the census data shown in Fig. 5. As described in detail by Boyd et al., (2014), two urban nuclei co-exist in Maputo: the formerly “white” neighbourhoods, downtown, where the estimated household income is relatively high; and the informal settlements on the outskirts of the city, which were initially established to accommodate the indigenous population and then, during the first decades of the twentieth century, received many immigrants from other parts of Africa and the Middle East. In addition to poverty, Maputo’s peri-urban communities suffer from a general lack of urban planning and construction standards, which further amplify their vulnerability to flooding.

Household income, as estimated via proxy means testing (PMT) carried out by the GoM and reported in Sohnesen et al., (2021), is here used as a determinant of social vulnerability. Poorer people tend to have less resilient dwellings, lesser financial resources to draw upon after a flood, greater professional insecurity, and reduced access to healthcare, all of which contribute to worse outcomes on the aftermath of a flood. Additional social and demographic factors can also influence vulnerability, including age, gender, health status, employment status etc. Exploiting the only relevant, available datasets, we consider the factor of age through consideration of the locations of schools (Fig. 6(a)), where children are naturally expected to concentrate. Furthermore, we use the location of hospitals to incorporate the vulnerability of groups that have underlying health conditions (Fig. 6(b)). Aggregation of vulnerable populations in these locations is considered by the introduction of high-vulnerability zones at a radius of 0.5 km from the center of schools and hospitals. In the respective layers (Fig. 6), vulnerability is assumed to decrease with spatial distance from the location of the critical facility. A radius of influence of 6 km is assumed to enclose every facility. We create an integrated layer of social vulnerability (V) estimated as the resultant of the three components, namely poverty (P), distance from schools (d_S), and distance from health facilities (d_H):

$$V = \frac{1}{3}P + \frac{1}{3}d_S + \frac{1}{3}d_H \quad (2)$$

Flood risk (R) is analyzed following the INFORM methodology (Marin-Ferrer et al., 2017), a recently developed framework proposed by the UN for the evaluation of risk from natural and manmade hazards in regions where human vulnerability is significant, as is the case in GMA. As implied by the flowchart of Fig. 2, R is the resultant of four components: hazard (H), exposure (E), vulnerability, and the lack of coping capacity (L). While the component of vulnerability considers the susceptibility of individuals and households, the component of coping capacity considers the dimension of institutional resources for alleviating disaster impacts. Coping capacity encloses policies for disaster risk reduction and the presence and functionality of basic infrastructure for response and recovery. Having no information about the coping capacity in GMA at the district (neighbourhood) level, we have here considered it to be uniform in the study area.

Risk is calculated according to Equation (3)

$$R = (H \& E) \times V \times L \quad (3)$$

Figure 7 shows a map of the flood risk index in the study area, classified in the same five categories as hazard, from very low to very high.

Figure 5. (a) Exposure of human population (people per square meter) and map of (b) socioeconomic vulnerability in terms of poverty, based on the latest nationally representative household survey (Sohnesen et al., 2021). Note that the proxy means testing (PMT) method makes use of observable characteristics of the household or its members to estimate their incomes or consumption, when other income data (salary slips, tax returns) are unavailable or unreliable. In this study (Sohnesen et al., 2021), household income was determined based on questionnaires surveying: the household size, the number of children, the level of residents' education, the number of house rooms, the existence of water sanitation, connection to electricity grid, and possession of electronic devices, such as TV, radio, and computer.

Figure 6. Locations of critical facilities associated with aggregation of vulnerable groups (a) schools and (b) hospitals. Contours indicate spatial proximity.

Figure 7. Map of flood risk for the baseline (current climate) hazard scenario.

CONCLUSIONS

The paper describes a GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis of flood risk for road infrastructure and communities in the metropolitan area of Maputo, Mozambique. The approach makes use of a multitude of disparate datasets, including climatologic parameters, a new digital map of ground elevation appropriate for hydrologic analysis, the spatial distribution of the road network and of critical facilities associated with the presence of vulnerable groups, inventorying of historic floods in the region, and demographic data relevant to population density and poverty. We have mapped and classified present and future flood susceptibility at a regional level making use of climate change projections under SSP-5-8.5. Results indicate that segments of the primary and secondary road network amounting to a total length of 153 km are presently exposed to high or very high flood susceptibility. A 60% increase of this number would be expected by 2040, under pessimistic assumptions for climate and land-use change.

Through an integrated analysis that considers social vulnerabilities and the reduced capacity of vulnerable groups to cope with natural disasters, the paper presents a regional flood risk map that can be used to prioritize interventions for upgrading and adaptation of the road infrastructure with the prospect to reduce inequalities and alleviate the marginalization and the vulnerability in Maputo's peri-urban communities. The framework presented can be used as a benchmark to tackle similar challenges in developing countries in the face of natural disasters and sustained natural stressors due to climate change.

LIMITATIONS

The reader should bear in mind that the reported flood hazard indexing is qualitative in nature. Areas of low flood susceptibility (Fig. 4) are less likely to flood in comparison to high or very high susceptibility areas. Inundation of low susceptibility areas remains possible, depending on the hazard intensity.

The classification and weighting of flood controlling parameters have been based on engineering judgment and validated against the available data on historic flooding. Recalibration of the model might be necessary if additional data become available. Furthermore, the effect of man-made drainage infrastructure has been neglected, due to its sparsity. This omission may lead to the overestimation of hazards in the limited areas where adequate drainage infrastructure (trenches, pipes, culverts, etc.) is present.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The first author acknowledges funding by the European Union H2020-Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research Grants Scheme MSCA-IF-2019 (No. 895432: ReBounce).

The basis analysis was completed thanks to the generous funding provided by the Public-Private Infrastructure Advisory Facility (PPIAF) through its Climate Resilience & Environmental Sustainability Technical Advisory (CREST) initiative².

REFERENCES

- Arabameri, A., Rezaei, K., Cerdà, A., Conoscenti, C., & Kalantari, Z. (2019). A comparison of statistical methods and multi-criteria decision making to map flood hazard susceptibility in Northern Iran. *Science of the Total Environment*, 660, 443–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.021>
- Bailey, R., Saffioti, C., & Drall, S. (2021). *Sunk costs: The socioeconomic impacts of flooding*. 33. https://www.marshmcclennan.com/content/dam/mmc-web/insights/publications/2021/june/Sunk-Cost_Socioeconomic-impacts-of-flooding_vF.pdf

² PPIAF is a multi-donor trust fund housed in the World Bank Group that provides technical assistance to governments in developing countries. PPIAF's main goal is to create enabling environments through high-impact partnerships that facilitate private investment in infrastructure. For more information, visit www.ppiaf.org. CREST is an initiative that aims to complement and enhance PPIAF's technical assistance by bringing a climate adaptation angle that maximizes its impact

- Bates, P. D. (2022). Flood Inundation Prediction. *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, 54(1), 287–315. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-fluid-030121-113138>
- Boyd, E., Ensor, J., Broto, V. C., & Juhola, S. (2014). Environmentalities of urban climate governance in Maputo, Mozambique. *Global Environmental Change*, 26, 140–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.03.012>
- Cremen, G., Galasso, C., & McCloskey, J. (2022). Modelling and quantifying tomorrow's risks from natural hazards. *Science of the Total Environment*, 817, 152552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152552>
- Dodangeh, E., Choubin, B., Eigdir, A. N., Nabipour, N., Panahi, M., Shamshirband, S., & Mosavi, A. (2020). Integrated machine learning methods with resampling algorithms for flood susceptibility prediction. *Science of the Total Environment*, 705. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135983>
- Hawker, L., Uhe, P., Paulo, L., Sosa, J., Savage, J., Sampson, C., & Neal, J. (2022). A 30 m global map of elevation with forests and buildings removed. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(2), 024016. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac4d4f>
- JICA, 2014: Comprehensive Urban Transport Master Plan for the Greater Maputo – Final Report Volume 2.
- JRC. (2021). *INFORM - Global, open-source risk assessment for humanitarian crises and disasters*. <http://www.inform-index.org/>.
- Kazakis, N., Kougias, I., & Patsialis, T. (2015). Assessment of flood hazard areas at a regional scale using an index-based approach and Analytical Hierarchy Process: Application in Rhodope-Evros region, Greece. *Science of the Total Environment*, 538, 555–563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.08.055>
- Li, X. H., Zhang, Q., Shao, M., & Li, Y. L. (2011). A Comparison of Parameter Estimation for Distributed Hydrological Modelling Using Automatic and Manual Methods. *Advanced Materials Research*, 356–360, 2372–2375. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.356-360.2372>
- Lyu, H. M., Sun, W. J., Shen, S. L., & Arulrajah, A. (2018). Flood risk assessment in metro systems of mega-cities using a GIS-based modeling approach. *Science of the Total Environment*, 626, 1012–1025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.01.138>
- Mahmoud, S. H., & Gan, T. Y. (2018). Urbanization and climate change implications in flood risk management: Developing an efficient decision support system for flood susceptibility mapping. *Science of the Total Environment*, 636, 152–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.282>
- Marin-Ferrer, M., Vernaccini, L. and Poljansek, K., Index for Risk Management INFORM Concept and Methodology Report — Version 2017, EUR 28655 EN, doi:10.2760/094023
- O'Neill, B. C., Tebaldi, C., Van Vuuren, D. P., Eyring, V., Friedlingstein, P., Hurtt, G., Knutti, R., Kriegler, E., Lamarque, J. F., Lowe, J., Meehl, G. A., Moss, R., Riahi, K., & Sanderson, B. M. (2016). The Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP) for CMIP6. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9(9), 3461–3482. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-3461-2016>
- Phongsapan, K., Chishtie, F., Poortinga, A., Bhandari, B., Meechaiya, C., Kunlamai, T., Aung, K. S., Saah, D., Anderson, E., Markert, K., Markert, A., & Towashiraporn, P. (2019). Operational Flood Risk Index Mapping for Disaster Risk Reduction Using Earth Observations and Cloud Computing Technologies: A Case Study on Myanmar. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 7(December), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2019.00191>
- Quadrante (2014). General Engineering Study for Preliminary Urban Mobility Project in Maputo Report. Prepared for the Maputo Municipality.
- Rentschler, J., & Salhab, M. (2020). *People in Harm's Way: Flood Exposure and Poverty in 189 Countries*. Policy Research Working Paper; No. 9447. October, Policy Working Paper 9447. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/34655>
- Saaty, Thomas L., 1990. How to make a decision: the analytic hierarchy process (ISSN 03772217).
- Saaty, T. L., & Vargas, L. G. (1998). Diagnosis with Dependent Symptoms: Bayes Theorem and the Analytic Hierarchy Process. *Operations Research*, 46(4), 491–502. <https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.46.4.491>
- Sohnesen, T. P., Fisker, P., & Malmgren-Hansen, D. (2021). Using Satellite Data to Guide Urban Poverty Reduction. *Review of Income and Wealth*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/roiw.12552>
- Tang, Z., Zhang, H., Yi, S., & Xiao, Y. (2018). Assessment of flood susceptible areas using spatially explicit, probabilistic multi-criteria decision analysis. *Journal of Hydrology*, 558, 144–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.01.033>
- Wing, O. E. J., Lehman, W., Bates, P. D., Sampson, C. C., Quinn, N., Smith, A. M., Neal, J. C., Porter, J. R., & Kousky, C. (2022). Inequitable patterns of US flood risk in the Anthropocene. *Nature Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01265-6>